

HOW SCIENTIFIC REASONING CORRELATES WITH HEALTH-RELATED BELIEFS AND BEHAVIORS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC?

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How scientific reasoning correlates with health-related beliefs and behaviors during the COVID-19 pandemic?

Abstract

We examined whether scientific reasoning is associated with health-related beliefs and behaviors over and above general analytic thinking ability in the general public ($N = 783$, aged 18–84). Health-related beliefs included: anti-vaccination attitudes, COVID-19 conspiracy beliefs, and generic health-related epistemically suspect beliefs. Scientific reasoning correlated with generic pseudoscientific and health-related conspiracy beliefs and COVID-19 conspiracy beliefs. Crucially, scientific reasoning was a stronger independent predictor of unfounded beliefs (including anti-vaccination attitudes) than general analytic thinking was; however, it had a more modest role in health-related behaviors.

Key words: scientific reasoning, analytic thinking, COVID-19 conspiracy beliefs, anti-vaccination attitudes, preventive behavior, COVID-19

Introduction

In disasters brought out by natural hazards, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, people are reminded of the importance of scientific reasoning, given that natural disasters cannot be fully prevented (Weichselgartner, 2001). Viruses are here to stay and so we have to learn to live with them while looking for effective treatments and vaccines. Scientific reasoning is therefore crucial – not only for understanding the causes and consequences of natural hazards, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, but also for sifting through the large amount of conflicting (and often false) information in the media and social networks. People with better scientific reasoning tend to subscribe to the scientific consensus (Drummond & Fischhoff, 2017a), hold fewer general unfounded beliefs (Čavojová et al., 2020) and question the efficacy of alternative medicine more (Čavojová & Ersoy, 2020). In this paper, we expand this line of research by further examining scientific reasoning as a predictor of health-related beliefs and behavior specific to the COVID-19 pandemic over and above general analytic thinking ability.

Scientific reasoning and analytic thinking

Scientific reasoning does not mean simply having more science knowledge. Rather, we use the term scientific reasoning to signify the ability to understand the methods and principles of scientific inquiry and the acquisition of the skills required to formulate, test, and revise theories and reflect on the process of generating evidence; or, more specifically, it signifies the “application of the methods or principles of scientific inquiry to reasoning or problem-solving situations” (Zimmerman, 2007, p. 173). In this sense, scientific reasoning is a subset of critical thinking skills that helps people reason about any complex content; and, despite its name, it is not something only scientists have. The ability to reason scientifically helps

individuals function properly in society and make informed decisions about health, behavior, and public policy (Trefil, 2008). Therefore, it is important that people are able to judge whether the evidence is consistent with the claims presented (theory–evidence coordination, Shah et al., 2017) and distinguish reliable information from disinformation, for example in relation to the COVID-19 outbreak.

Needless to say, scientific reasoning and scientific knowledge are interconnected. People with better scientific reasoning tend to have more science-related knowledge (Dieckmann & Johnson, 2019; Drummond & Fischhoff, 2017a; Kaygısız & Gürkan, 2018). Additionally, and more importantly for the present study, people with better scientific reasoning are better able to interpret numerical information on the effectiveness and side effects of certain drugs (Drummond & Fischhoff, 2017a). This suggests that people with better scientific reasoning do not just know more scientific facts or subscribe more strongly to the scientific consensus, but are also able to use probabilistic and numerical information to make more informed choices about over-the-counter medication and health-related advice.

On the other hand, the relationship between knowledge of science facts and scientific understanding is not straightforward – while the two are correlated, the correlations are modest at best (Johnson, 2003). This also suggests that there are limits to assessing science understanding using knowledge-based tests alone. This issue was addressed recently by Drummond and Fischhof (2017), who devised the Scientific Reasoning Scale (SRS). It consists of eleven short scenarios designed to measure a person’s ability to evaluate evidence for conclusions drawn from fictional scenarios, and has been successfully used and validated in non-English speaking countries (Bašnáková et al., n.d.; Kaygısız & Gürkan, 2018).

It is important to distinguish scientific reasoning from more general analytic thinking. The concept of analytic thinking is rooted in dual process theories that pitch analytic thinking against intuitive thinking (Epstein et al., 1996; Kahneman, 2011; Toplak et al., 2014). Dual

process theories usually see intuitive thinking as fast, autonomous, and effortless, while analytic thinking is deliberate, effortful, and requires working memory resources. These two processes are most evident during conflict tasks, which evoke a strong intuitive, but incorrect response and require deliberate analytic thinking if the right answer is to be reached. One such task typically used to investigate these two processes is the Cognitive Reflection Test (Frederick, 2005) and modified versions (e.g. Sirota et al., 2019; Šrol & Neys, n.d.).

Importantly, a recent review of dual process theory (Stanovich, 2011) claims that people fail to behave and reason rationally not simply because they fail to suppress false intuitions, but because they lack the appropriate knowledge as well (termed mindware in parallel to computer software). Several studies have shown that mindware instantiation predicts successful reasoning over and above analytic thinking on its own (Čavojová et al., 2020; Klaczynski, 2014; Šrol & Neys, n.d.). Čavojová et al. (2020) examined scientific reasoning as an example of specific mindware and showed it was a significant predictor contributing to susceptibility to both cognitive biases and epistemically suspect beliefs over and above the other cognitive predictors. These results suggest that scientific reasoning is an important factor in protecting against epistemically suspect beliefs and in aiding better decision making among the non-scientific population. We expect these results will be replicated in the current study examining health-related epistemically suspect beliefs and behaviors. This expectation is also based on another study, which distinguished the priming effects of scientific reasoning from more general analytic thinking (Drummond & Fischhoff, 2019). In this paper, therefore, we measure participants' level of analytic thinking as well as their scientific reasoning and we expect that scientific reasoning will be correlated to various health-related behaviors and beliefs.

Link between epistemically suspect beliefs, health-related behavior and scientific reasoning

Belief is an attitude that something is true and as such it is considered to be the simplest form of mental representation. For a belief to be valid, it has to be based on reality and evidence.

Beliefs that are not substantiated by evidence or that contradict current knowledge or naturalistic conceptions of the world have been labeled epistemically suspect beliefs (Lobato et al., 2014; Pennycook et al., 2015).

The connection between epistemically suspect beliefs and scientific reasoning is reflected in three complementary lines of research. First, there are studies showing that people with better scientific reasoning hold beliefs that are more consistent with the scientific consensus (Drummond & Fischhoff, 2017a). Second, better scientific reasoning skills are rooted in the understanding that the scientific method is the best known way of acquiring beliefs and knowledge that most accurately reflect the world; people with better scientific reasoning understand the process of science better (Bašnáková, Čavojová, & Šrol, n.d.). Third, people with better scientific reasoning tend to have fewer epistemically suspect beliefs (Čavojová et al., 2020).

The role of cognitive factors, such as beliefs, in health-related behavior has been extensively studied. One of the most influential models is the Health Belief Model (Rosenstock, 2005), which holds that a person will engage in any given behavior if the health benefits outweigh the barriers.

The effect of epistemically suspect beliefs on health-related behavior is more visible with pseudoscientific theories, as belief in the efficacy of ineffective treatments can lead to poorer health choices, such as refusing vaccinations or conventional treatments (Boström & Rössner, 1990; Farrington et al., 2018; Saint-Victor & Omer, 2013). However, pseudoscientific

explanations are often interconnected with conspiracy theories, such as the idea that Big Pharma is hiding the cure for cancer so it can make more money, and other magical beliefs and superstitious thinking (Grimmer & White, 1992; Lindeman et al., 2000; Preece & Baxter, 2000; Saher & Lindeman, 2005).

Scientific reasoning and its role in health-related behavior and beliefs has mostly been studied indirectly – for instance, by comparing science and non-science students. For example, Grimmer and White (1992) compared medicine, science, and art students in their endorsement of epistemically suspect beliefs and found that medical students showed the lowest level of pseudoscientific beliefs, probably a result of their having studied science extensively since high school. In a similar vein, other studies have shown that trust in questionable health practices and pseudoscience beliefs correlates somewhat with a college education and attending science courses, although the results are often inconclusive (Jahoda, 1968; Pasachoff et al., 1970; Tobacyk, 1984; Warburton, 1956).

Another line of research that has indirectly linked science reasoning with health behavior is health literacy (Zeyer, 2012). Zeyer (2012) claims that health literacy is inherently knowledge-based and that this reveals there is a strong link between scientific literacy and health literacy. Neter and Brainin (2019) examined the relationship between health literacy and health outcomes in 80 published studies and found a consistent negative association between health literacy and mortality, a positive association between health literacy and medication management/adherence, and other diverse health-related behaviors such as physical exercise, vaccinations, cancer screening, self-care, appointment keeping, or using an inhaler.

As far as we know, only a couple of studies have directly examined the role of scientific reasoning in health-related behavior. Čavojová and Ersoy (2020) found that people with higher scientific reasoning skills believe less in the efficacy of complementary and alternative medicine and use them less often. Sarathchandra et al. (2018) examined scientific reasoning in connection with vaccine acceptance, which is another example of a health behavior, and found that scientific reasoning had a small positive effect on three facets of vaccine acceptance.

Thus, although we expect that scientific reasoning will correlate with attitudes to vaccination in our sample, we were also interested in another related question. Only a very small percentage of people are voluntarily vaccinated against preventable diseases, such as seasonal flu (about 5% in Slovakia, where our study took place), and that is despite the cost being covered by health insurance companies. We wondered whether people will change their attitude to vaccination due to COVID-19. We therefore examined whether people with negative attitudes toward vaccination would be eager to be vaccinated against COVID-19 if such a vaccine were available.

Aims and hypotheses

In the present study, we examined whether scientific reasoning ability correlates with a range of health-related beliefs and behaviors more strongly than general analytic thinking ability. Based on the indirect evidence reviewed above concerning scientific reasoning and health-related behavior and research, we developed four general hypotheses:

1. We expected scientific reasoning to correlate positively with coronavirus knowledge and negatively with coronavirus conspiracy beliefs, generic health-related epistemically suspect beliefs, and anti-vaccination attitudes.

2. We expected scientific reasoning to correlate positively with flu vaccination and willingness to get the coronavirus vaccination.
3. We expected scientific reasoning to be a better predictor than analytic thinking of health-related beliefs.
4. We expected people with higher scientific reasoning to report better take-up of preventive measures recommended by the medical authorities and less take-up of unofficial health measures than people with moderate and weak scientific reasoning ability.

Methods

Context of the study

We collected the data between March 13 and 22, 2020 (the first confirmed case of COVID-19 in Slovakia was reported on March 6, 2020). During this period, the number of confirmed COVID-19 cases had grown from 32 to 185. On March 16th, the Slovak government unveiled strict preventive actions that were implemented gradually. These included limits on all personal foreign travel, compulsory quarantine for people entering the country, and the closure of schools and most non-essential shops and services.

Participants

The sample consisted of 976 participants who filled in an online survey created in Qualtrics, either in response to a request on social media or an invitation from a participant recruitment agency. The survey consisted of six blocks of questions: socio-demographic questions, vaccination behavior and beliefs, preventive behavior, threat perception, epistemically suspect

beliefs, scientific reasoning, and analytic thinking¹. The average time taken to complete the whole survey was 40.6 minutes.

Data relating to 193 participants were omitted from all further analysis as they did not pass the attention check controls. The final sample consisted of 783 participants (417 females, 363 males, 3 preferred not to disclose their gender). Participants were aged 18–84 years ($M = 42.00$, $SD = 16.84$). In Table S1, we present more detailed demographic information on the final sample.

Instruments

Descriptive statistics and internal consistency estimates for all materials can be found in Table 1.

Scientific reasoning and general analytic thinking ability.

Scientific reasoning. Scientific reasoning ability was measured using six items based on the Scientific Reasoning Scale (Bašňáková et al., n.d.; Drummond & Fischhoff, 2017a) which measures six validity issues in evaluating evidence: blinding, causation versus correlation, confounding variables, construct validity, control group, ecological validity, and random assignment to conditions. For example, the “causation versus correlation” item was about increasing birth rate (“The researchers want to find out how to increase natality. They ask for statistical information and see that there are more children born in cities that have more hospitals. This finding implies that building new hospitals will increase the birth rate of the population. Participants responded to items by selecting one of the options: *Agree/Disagree*.”).

¹ The data were collected as part of a larger study on beliefs and behaviors relating to the COVID-19 pandemic. In a previous study (blinded), we focused on feelings of anxiety and lack of control associated with the COVID-19 pandemic and their relationship to increased endorsement of various epistemically suspect beliefs. Neither scientific reasoning nor health-related behaviors – the focus of the present study – were analyzed.

Analytic thinking ability. To measure general analytic thinking ability, we used six items that evoked compelling but wrong intuitive responses. Three of the items were taken from the Cognitive Reflection Test by Frederick (2005) with modified content. The other three items were from the verbal version of the Cognitive Reflection Test (Sirota et al., 2019). The sum of correct answers on the six items was used as the measure of a participant's analytic thinking ability.

Health-related beliefs:

Coronavirus conspiracy beliefs. Participants indicated their agreement with 10 statements describing various conspiracy theories about the outbreak, spread, and potential treatment of the novel coronavirus on a 5-point scale and the average rating was used to represent endorsement of coronavirus conspiracy beliefs.

Coronavirus knowledge. Eight knowledge items (4 true, 4 false) were used to assess knowledge of COVID-19. Participants indicated their agreement on a 5-point scale and the average rating for four true knowledge items and four false knowledge items was used.

Generic health-related epistemically suspect beliefs. To measure the endorsement of generic epistemically suspect beliefs, seven health-related items from a survey of epistemically suspect beliefs by Šrol (n.d.) were used. The items dealt with the effectiveness of various alternative treatments (homeopathy, reiki, oral use of chlorine dioxide) for serious illnesses and the conspiracy motives of the medical and pharmaceutical industry. Participants indicated their agreement on a 5-point scale and the average rating on the seven items was used as the measure of generic health-related epistemically suspect beliefs.

Anti-vaccination attitudes. Ten items were used to measure negative attitudes toward vaccination. Six were adapted from Wallace et al. (2019) and four items were constructed by

the authors. Participants indicated their agreement on a 5-point scale. Higher scores indicated stronger anti-vaccination attitudes.

Self-reported health-related behavior:

Preventive behavior. We measured preventive behavior by presenting participants with 19 behaviors recommended by medical authorities and government, as well as non-standard preventive measures recommended on social networks (e.g. I don't leave my home and, if possible, I work from home; I drink at least 52% spirit for disinfection purposes). Participants answered either "yes" (1) or "no" (0). Our original plan was to distinguish between the standard recommended measures and the non-standard unfounded preventive measures – and conduct the analyses on these two composite scores. However, the preliminary exploratory factor analysis indicated that the factorial structure of the preventive behaviors in our questionnaire was far more complex and no simple meaningful factorial solution could be obtained. Therefore, we decided to analyze each preventive behavior separately.

Vaccination. Two questions were used: (1) did you get the flu vaccine for this season (1 = yes, 2 = I intended to, but missed the deadline, 3 = no); and (2) will you get the coronavirus vaccine if one becomes available?, on a 5-point scale (1 = definitely yes, 5 = definitely no). In response to the first question 8.4 % indicated that they had not had the flu vaccine, 10.6 % indicated that they had intended to get the flu vaccine but had not managed to do so before it was too late, and 81% of participants had not had the flu vaccine. Because of the low percentage of vaccinated participants, we created a single category for the further analyses containing those who had received the flu vaccine and those who had intended to get the flu vaccine.

Data analysis

As the first step in our analysis, we conducted a confirmatory factor analysis to test the factorial structure of our questionnaire, which contained both previously used and newly created materials. The results are presented in the supplementary materials. The confirmatory factor analysis model with seven factors representing factual information, false statements, COVID-19 conspiracy beliefs, generic unfounded health-related beliefs, anti-vaccination attitudes, scientific reasoning, and analytic thinking showed a good fit to the present data².

Then, we examined the relationships among the main variables (H1, H2) in the study using the correlation analysis. As the next step, we conducted a hierarchical multiple linear regression analysis to test whether scientific reasoning predicts a composite of unfounded health-related beliefs over and above general analytic thinking ability (H3).

Finally, to compare health behaviors among people with different levels of scientific reasoning (H4), we split our sample into three groups based on the SRS scores: 24.2% participants in the lowest scoring group (≤ 3), 43.6% participants in the mid-scoring group (≤ 5) and 32.2% participants in the highest scoring group (≥ 6). One-way ANOVA analyses with the SRS group as a between-subject factor were used to determine whether people with different levels of scientific reasoning differed significantly in reported preventive behaviors. Significant pairwise differences were identified through Bonferroni corrected post-hoc comparisons.

The conventional threshold of $p < .05$ was used to determine statistical significance in all the analyses presented below. Because of the large number of statistical tests conducted in the correlation analysis and comparisons of preventive behaviors across people with different levels

² However, the confirmatory factor analysis showed that one of the items pertaining to factual information about COVID-19 showed a very low loading on its respective factor (see supplementary materials for details). We therefore decided to exclude this item and use the remaining three items in the subsequent analyses of factual information about the coronavirus).

of scientific reasoning, we used Bonferroni corrected significance thresholds in these analyses to keep the probability of Type I errors at 5%.

Data Sharing Statement

The current article includes the complete raw data-set collected in the study including the participants' data set, syntax file and log files for analysis. Pending acceptance for publication, all of the data files will be automatically uploaded to the Figshare repository.

Results

Correlations between scientific reasoning & analytic thinking and health-related beliefs & knowledge

Correlations among the main variables are reported in Table 1. As expected, scientific reasoning correlated negatively with coronavirus conspiracy beliefs, unfounded general health-related beliefs, and anti-vaccination attitudes. The same pattern of negative correlations (albeit weaker) occurred with general analytic thinking. Similarly, we found a negative correlation between scientific reasoning and accepting false facts about coronavirus as true. The same pattern was observed with analytic thinking. On the other hand, correctly accepting coronavirus facts as true correlated positively only with scientific reasoning, albeit weakly. There was no correlation with analytic thinking. Generally, people were able to correctly identify most coronavirus facts (Table 1) but the stronger correlation with scientific reasoning may suggest that more scientifically sophisticated people looked for more detailed coronavirus information and thus were better able to distinguish the facts from the misinformation.

Table 1. Correlations among scientific reasoning, analytic thinking ability, and health-related beliefs and behaviors

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	α	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.
1. scientific reasoning	4.52	1.41	.56	1							
2. analytic thinking	2.67	1.83	.70	.36	1						
3. coronavirus conspiracy beliefs	2.07	0.87	.90	-.44	-.27	1					
4. coronavirus facts	4.36	0.71	.50	.16	.08	-.18	1				
5. coronavirus false	2.28	0.91	.68	-.48	-.31	.63	-.13	1			
6. health-related unfounded beliefs	2.40	0.78	.81	-.43	-.23	.72	-.14	.60	1		
7. anti-vaccination attitudes	2.12	0.83	.88	-.22	-.15	.35	-.17	.31	.44	1	
8. refusal of covid vaccination	2.09	1.06	–	–.02	.01	.14	–.09	.06	.20	.45	1
9. flu vaccination	0.19 ^a	0.39	–	–.03	.03	–.08	–.07	–.02	–.12	–.24	–.32

Note. Correlations are based on 783 observations. ^aFlu vaccination 0 = no, 1 = yes/had intended to. Correlations presented in bold are significant at $p < .00139$ (the threshold for significance was Bonferroni corrected for 36 statistical tests).

Does scientific reasoning predict health-related beliefs over analytic thinking?

Next, we examined whether general analytic thinking and scientific behavior independently predict health-related beliefs. To reduce the number of analyses, we computed a composite score for health-related beliefs as the average score of all items comprising the four scales (coronavirus conspiracy theories, false coronavirus statements, health-related epistemically suspect beliefs, and anti-vaccination attitudes). The composite score showed excellent internal reliability ($M = 2.19$, $SD = .67$, $\alpha = .93$).

Table 2. Summary of the regression analyses predicting health-related beliefs

	Health-related beliefs				
	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
(Constant)	2.471	0.041		60.846	< .001
Analytic thinking	-0.105	0.013	-0.29	-8.400	< .001
$F = 70.55, p < .001, R^2 = .082$					
(Constant)	3.229	0.070		45.895	< .001
Analytic thinking	-0.050	0.012	-0.14	-4.114	< .001
Scientific reasoning	-0.200	0.016	-0.42	-12.675	< .001
$F = 160.67, p < .001, R^2 = .238$					

Note. The table shows unstandardized (*B*) and standardized (β) regression coefficients with their respective *t*-values and significance. Model statistics (F-test with the proportion of explained variance in the outcome variable) are shown in the last row.

In our regression analysis (Table 2) analytic thinking and scientific reasoning together explained 23.8% of total variance for health-related beliefs. Crucially, scientific reasoning emerged as a stronger predictor than analytic thinking. This suggests the effect of scientific reasoning is distinguishable from a general tendency to think analytically.

Comparison of self-reported health-related behaviors among participants with different levels of scientific reasoning

Lastly, we compared various preventive behaviors among people with high, moderate, and low levels of scientific reasoning ability (Table 3).

Table 3. Engagement in various preventive behaviors in lowest, medium and highest scoring participants in SRS

	lowest SRS		medium SRS		highest SRS		<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
I wash my hands with soap for at least 20 seconds.	0.92	0.28	0.96	0.23	1.00	0.32	5.86	.003
I disinfect household surfaces more often.	0.73	0.45	0.71	0.46	0.74	0.44	0.40	.673
I cough and sneeze into paper tissues and immediately put them in the bin.	0.85 _a	0.36	0.79 _a	0.41	0.63 _b	0.48	16.62	< .001
I don't go to places where there are large numbers of people (e.g. cultural and sports events, public transportation)	0.96 _a	0.19	0.92 _a	0.27	0.86 _b	0.35	7.94	< .001
I stocked up on food and water.	0.50 _a	0.50	0.57 _a	0.50	0.69 _b	0.46	9.46	< .001
I stocked up on medical supplies.	0.39	0.49	0.37	0.48	0.39	0.49	0.14	.872
I wear a facial mask to protect myself against infection.	0.69 _a	0.47	0.63 _a	0.48	0.52 _b	0.50	7.38	.001
I don't leave the house and work from home if I can or take leave.	0.72	0.45	0.71	0.46	0.64	0.48	2.39	.092
I wear a facial mask so as not to infect others.	0.71	0.45	0.78	0.41	0.79	0.41	2.08	.125
I use chlorine- or alcohol-based sprays.	0.16 _a	0.37	0.24 _a	0.43	0.33 _b	0.47	9.02	< .001
I use a nasal saline solution.	0.09	0.29	0.07	0.25	0.02	0.14	5.50	.004
I drink warm water.	0.22	0.42	0.14	0.35	0.11	0.31	5.99	.003
I drink at least 52% spirit for disinfection purposes.	0.12	0.33	0.12	0.33	0.09	0.28	0.98	.377
I avoid drafts and breezes.	0.49 _a	0.50	0.38 _b	0.49	0.23 _c	0.42	17.29	< .001
I dress more warmly.	0.42 _a	0.50	0.28 _b	0.45	0.25 _b	0.44	7.80	< .001
I build up resistance by taking cold showers, wearing less clothing, and going out in the fresh air more often.	0.47 _a	0.50	0.29 _b	0.46	0.23 _b	0.42	14.58	< .001
I eat more fruit and vegetables.	0.75 _a	0.43	0.65 _a	0.48	0.54 _b	0.50	10.93	< .001
I try to go out in the fresh air for at least 20 minutes every day.	0.83	0.38	0.77	0.42	0.73	0.45	3.00	.050
I do some active sport.	0.34 _a	0.47	0.41 _{a,b}	0.49	0.50 _b	0.50	6.39	.002

Notes. The table shows comparisons of mean self-reported engagement in various standard recommended and non-standard or scientifically unfounded preventive behaviors among people with lowest, moderate, and highest levels of scientific reasoning. The columns on the right show the results of the one-way ANOVA for each behavior, with the scientific reasoning group (lowest, moderate, highest) as a between-subject factor. Statistically significant ANOVA results are presented in bold (the threshold for significance, $p < .0026$, was Bonferroni corrected for 19 statistical tests). Underlined values represent the group mean that differed significantly from the means of other groups for that respective behavior. For significant overall ANOVA results, we used Bonferroni corrected post-hoc tests to identify significant pairwise differences. These are indicated by lower-index letters in the

respective rows. Group means with different lower-index letters (a, b) indicate significant difference between groups. Group mean with the same lower-index letter indicates that the groups did not differ significantly from each other ($p > .05$).

Results showed that participants with high scientific reasoning reported significantly more efforts to stock up on food and water, use chlorine- and alcohol-based sprays, and actively do sport than the two lower-scoring groups did. On the other hand, participants with the lowest scientific reasoning reported significantly more efforts to avoid drafts and breezes, wear warmer clothes, build up resilience using cold water, and eat more fruit and vegetables.

We also performed t-tests to analyze the differences in scientific reasoning and analytic thinking between those who got or intended to get the flu vaccine and those who did not. We did not find any significant differences in scientific reasoning ($t = 0.72, p = .472$) nor in general analytic thinking ($t = -.083, p = .405$) between the two groups.

Interestingly, we found no correlation between scientific reasoning and analytic thinking and the hypothetical question about willingness to get a coronavirus vaccine if available. This caught our attention so we performed several more exploratory analyses. We found a strong correlation between anti-vaccination attitudes and reluctance to get a hypothetical coronavirus vaccine ($r = .45, p < .001$), which suggests that people are quite consistent and generalize their reservations about vaccination to include the hypothetical coronavirus vaccine.

Discussion

Scientific reasoning and health-related beliefs

The most important finding of our study is that scientific reasoning correlates not only with general pseudoscientific and conspiracy beliefs about health – as has been shown in previous

research (Čavojová et al., 2020; Čavojová & Ersoy, 2020) – but also conspiracy beliefs relating specifically to COVID-19. This finding has important implications for understanding the generation and spread of various forms of misinformation following a disaster because it further corroborates the results of studies showing that people who have one kind of epistemically suspect belief tend to have other kinds of such beliefs as well (Čavojová et al., 2020; Lobato et al., 2014). In other words, people who believe in some conspiracy theories or pseudoscientific claims are more inclined to accept newly encountered misinformation.

People who were more scientifically sophisticated were better able to navigate the constantly updated coronavirus information and evaluate which information was more likely to be true and which was a conspiracy theory. This was reflected in the positive correlation between scientific reasoning and knowledge about the novel coronavirus, although the relationship was relatively weak, which is in line with previous research showing that knowledge of science facts does not necessarily lead to higher science understanding (Johnson, 2003). People with higher scientific reasoning were able to search for more COVID-19 information and consequently were better informed, or, possibly, people who searched for more COVID-19 information were forced to engage in more deliberative thinking which resulted in higher scientific reasoning. Participants in our sample obtained higher scores in scientific reasoning (75.3% success rate) in comparison with previous research (63.3% to 70% success rates in Bašňáková et al., n.d.; Drummond & Fischhoff, 2017). It may be that the COVID-19 outbreak forced people to seek more science-related information than usual and to engage in more effortful thinking.

Similarly, like Sarathchandra et al. (2018) we found that people with higher scientific reasoning had a more positive attitude to vaccination. Furthermore, our results clearly showed that anti-vaccination attitudes are associated with conspiracy thinking and holding more general epistemically suspect beliefs, as well as more COVID-19 conspiracy theories. This

can have real world implications, as we witnessed in our country shortly after the data collection when far-right politicians spread new vaccination conspiracies and the proportion of people willing to get a COVID-19 vaccine if available fell between March and May 2020³. Crucially, scientific reasoning correlated more strongly with unfounded beliefs (including false COVID-19 information and anti-vaccination attitudes) than the general analytic thinking. This result provides further support for the rationality model proposed by Stanovich (2011) showing that knowledge and understanding of science is at least as important as the propensity for analytical thinking. Similarly, like previous studies (Čavojová et al., 2020; Drummond & Fischhoff, 2019) we showed that scientific reasoning mindware is indispensable and correlates with health-related beliefs more strongly than a general tendency to think analytically.

Scientific reasoning and health behaviors

The results on vaccination uptake showed that the refusal of a potential COVID-19 vaccine is associated most strongly with anti-vaccination attitudes, but also with COVID-specific conspiracy theories and health-related epistemically suspect beliefs. Similarly, while there was no difference in scientific reasoning (and general analytic thinking) between those who had or intended to have the flu vaccine against this year and those who did not, flu vaccination was negatively associated with anti-vaccination attitudes and refusal of a COVID-19 vaccination. It seems that people with strong anti-vaccination attitudes (that correlated with other epistemically suspect beliefs) will refuse any vaccination – both existing and new ones – regardless of the information they receive. It is also possible that people with strong attitudes look for confirmative evidence and interpret the information in a more biased way (Čavojová et al., 2018; Klaczynski, 2000), which could explain why scientific reasoning played no role

³ https://www.sav.sk/index.php?lang=sk&doc=services-news&source_no=20&news_no=8837

in the variables related to vaccine uptake. Indeed, there is some evidence that when it comes to polarized issues – such as climate change or stem cell research – people with higher scientific literacy are not more likely to hold beliefs that are consistent with the scientific consensus but are even more polarized along the lines of their prior beliefs (e.g. Drummond & Fischhoff, 2017b). Similarly, higher scientific reasoning in people with strong anti-vaccination attitudes may mean they are better able to provide support for their worldview even when it contradicts the scientific consensus.

Contrary to our expectations, no clear pattern of association emerged between scientific reasoning and engaging in more sensible health practices.

For example, regardless of scientific reasoning, people reported the same amount of government-recommended health behaviors, such as hand washing, wearing facial masks to protect others, and working from home. On the other hand, people with lower scientific reasoning reported more efforts to avoid drafts and breezes, wear warm clothes more, use cold water to build up resilience, and eat more fruit and vegetables. Most of these belong to the category of so-called “momism” (Heinzen et al., 2015): things a person’s mother tells them and are believed to be true despite the lack of evidence for such claims. However, people with higher scientific reasoning reported stocking up on food and water more, using chlorine- and/or alcohol-based sprays, and doing active sports.

This pattern of differences may seem confusing, but there are several possible explanations.

The data collection took place at the beginning of the outbreak in Slovakia, when there was a large amount of conflicting information in the media – for instance, initial mainstream reports discouraged people from wearing face masks for self-protection (probably due to supply shortages), but on March 16th the Slovak government made face mask wearing compulsory in all public places. Similarly, some medical experts initially compared COVID-19 to a bad seasonal flu. The pattern of self-reported preventive behaviors against COVID-19 may partly

reflect skepticism of some measures and a reluctance to engage in panicky behavior by more scientifically sophisticated people.

Or, possibly, people with better scientific reasoning skills were able to focus on different aspects of the information – the daily reports of hundreds (absolute numbers) of new cases certainly seem like a high number, but people with higher scientific reasoning might look at the proportion of people infected in relation to the whole population, or other aspects of the numerical information, enabling them to view the high absolute numbers from a wider perspective. It is, therefore, possible that people with better scientific reasoning felt less intimidated by the often conflicting information presented by experts and the media at the beginning of the outbreak, and evaluated the situation as less dangerous than people with lower scientific reasoning.

Lastly, the intention–behavior gap has often been observed, especially in health-related behavior (Baumann et al., 2015; Cobb Leonard & Scott-Jones, 2010; Sheeran & Webb, 2016). It seems plausible that other – contextual or emotional – factors affected health behaviors during the early stages of the COVID-19 outbreak more strongly than the cognitive factors we examined.

Implications and recommendations

The rapidly changing situation at the beginning of the COVID-19 outbreak was the main factor that probably affected participants' responses and thus limits the interpretation of our findings. At the same time, it is also the main strength of our research because it offers a glimpse into how scientific reasoning can prove useful during a crisis like the COVID-19 one, as it enables people to evaluate new evidence and not fall prey to conspiracy theories and beliefs. Policymakers and educators should be aware that scientific reasoning plays an important role in preventing epistemically suspect beliefs (Čavojová et al., 2020) and that the

other strongest predictor of a new conspiracy or unfounded belief is holding other epistemically suspect beliefs (Lobato et al., 2014). Finally, several studies have shown that anxiety and feeling threatened tend to increase susceptibility to conspiracy explanations of events (J.-W. Van Prooijen, 2019; J. W. van Prooijen & Douglas, 2017). As a result, when a crisis strikes, such as a pandemic, it may already be too late to foster scientific reasoning – people rely on prior beliefs and attitudes when interpreting new evidence, and those who are more prone to epistemically suspect beliefs will be more vulnerable to misinformation.

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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